

Studies in Cyclohexenone Derivatives. Part II*

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ambiguous syntheses of 3,6- and 3,4-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-ones are described.

In connection with our studies^{1,2} in the formation of cyclohexenone derivatives by the Robinson-Mannich base reaction, authentic specimens of 3,6- and 3,4-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-ones (III and VI) were required. These compounds have already been described or referred to by several workers³⁻¹⁰. Most of the reported methods of preparation are, however, ambiguous. Besides, in some cases the ketones have not been properly characterised by solid derivatives. The authentic synthesis of these two ketones, as described by the present authors, incidentally, removes some of the earlier discrepancies in the literature.

Ethyl 3-methylcyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate¹¹ was methylated according to the usual procedure and the product (I) on bromination and dehydrobromination afforded the unsaturated keto-ester (II). This was smoothly hydrolysed by ethanolic alkali to 3,6-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (III) (semicarbazone m.p. 199-200°; dinitrophenylhydrazone m.p. 162-63° and 170-71°).

For the preparation of the isomeric ketone (VI), ethyl acetoacetate was alkylated successively with ethyl β -bromopropionate and methyl iodide, the product hydrolysed, esterified, and then cyclised to 2-methylcyclohexan-1,5-dione (IV).

*Ref. 1 may be regarded as Part I of this series.

1. Guha *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 267.
2. Guha and Nasipuri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 84.
3. Mousseron and Winternitz, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1945, **12**, 71.
4. Jacquier and Boyer, *ibid.*, 1955, **9**; Jacquier *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, 1653.
5. Colonge *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1900, **251**, 252.
6. Kochetkov and Gollikh, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1960, **30**, 048.
7. Dart and Henbest, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3563.
8. Decombe, *Compt. rend.*, 1937, **205**, 680.
9. Frank *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1379.
10. Baumgarten and Eifert, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **18**, 1177.
11. Kotz and Hesse, *Annalen*, 1905, **342**, 306; Black *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2971.

The latter was converted into isobutoxy derivative, possibly 2-methyl-5-isobutoxy-cyclohex-5-en-1-one (V) and thence to 3,4-dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (VI), by treatment with methylmagnesium iodide¹³, followed by dilute acid. The structure assigned to the isobutoxy derivative (V) seems to be correct both from the analogy of known cases¹³ and also from the properties of the final dimethylcyclohexenone (VI) which appeared to be homogeneous and was completely different from the alternative product (III), described above. The structure of the ketone (VI) was further confirmed by its identity with a ketone obtained by lithium-liquid ammonia reduction of 3, 4-dimethylanisole¹⁴.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 3,6-Dimethylcyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate (I).—To a suspension of the sodio-derivative of ethyl 3-methylcyclohexan-1-one-6-carboxylate, prepared from powdered sodium (4 g.) and the β -keto-ester (27.6 g.) in dry benzene (100 ml), methyl iodide (15 ml) was added and the whole refluxed on a water-bath for 15 hrs. with occasional addition of methyl iodide. The product was worked up in the usual way and on distillation afforded an oil (26 g.), b.p. 122-23°/15 mm. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 9.4. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.7; H, 9.1%). It gave negative ferric chloride reaction.

Ethyl 3,6-Dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one-6-carboxylate (II).—A solution of bromine (3 ml) in chloroform (35 ml) was gradually introduced into an ice-cold solution of the preceding keto-ester (12 g.) in the same solvent (115 ml). After the addition was complete, the cooled mixture was stirred for 2 hours longer and then left overnight. The almost colorless solution was taken up in a separating funnel and washed successively with water, saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution, and water. The residue after distillation *in vacuo* afforded a light yellow viscous liquid (14.5 g.), b.p. 115-20°/0.5 mm. This was mixed with γ -collidine (29 ml) and heated in an oil-bath at 150-60° for 1 hour. It was then poured into ice-cold HCl (conc., 50 ml) and water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed successively with H_2SO_4 (dil.), $NaHCO_3$ solution, and water. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was distilled to a colorless oil (8.4 g.), b.p. 125°/5 mm. (Found: C, 67.0; H, 8.2. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.3; H, 8.2%). The *dinitrophenylhydrazine* crystallised from benzeno-methanol in orange needles, m.p. 155-56°. (Found: C, 53.9; H, 5.4. $C_{17}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires C, 54.3; H, 5.3%).

12. Frank and Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1647.

13. Conroy, *ibid.*, 1952, 74, 3046; Vig *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 433; and also ref. 12.

14. Nasipuri and Guha, unpublished work.

3,6-Dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (III).—The above unsaturated keto-ester (5.2 g.) was heated with a solution of KOH (6 g.) in water (20 ml) and ethanol (10 ml) for 10 hours. It was then diluted with water, extracted with ether, and the ethereal layer dried (CaCl_2). The product was distilled to furnish a sweet-smelling liquid (3 g.), b.p. $78^\circ/15$ mm. (Found: C, 77.3; H, 10.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$: C, 77.4; H, 9.7%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 234 m μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.13); n_D^{25} 1.4771. The reported data are: λ_{max} 233 m μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.18)⁷, λ_{max} 236 ($\log \epsilon$, 4.10)⁴; n_D^{20} 1.4770⁵, 1.4867⁶, and 1.4845⁷.

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from dilute ethanol in white crystals, m.p. 199-200°. (Found: C, 59.9; H, 8.7; N, 22.6. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}_3$: C, 59.7; H, 8.3; N, 23.2%). The reported m.p.s. are 138° (ref. 3) and 186° (ref. 5). The di-*o*-phenylhydrazone crystallised from benzene-methanol in red needles, m.p. 135-50°, and were subsequently resolved into two components: (a) m.p. 162-63°; (b) m.p. 170-71° having the same elemental analysis in accordance with Dart and Henbest⁷. (Found: C, 55.7; H, 5.7; N, 18.8. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$: C, 55.3; H, 5.3; N, 18.4%). The mixed m.p. of the two D.N.P.s was 135-50°. Jacquier *et al.*⁴ report 123-24° and 153-54° for the m.p.s. of the two D.N.P.s.

Methyl 3-Methyl-2-ketopentane-5-carboxylate.—Ethyl α -acetylglutarate¹⁵ (58 g.), prepared by acylating ethyl acetoacetate with ethyl β -bromopropionate, was methylated by heating with powdered sodium (6.5 g.) and an excess of methyl iodide in dry benzene (150 ml) for 10 hours. The product was worked up in the usual way and finally distilled to furnish an oil (51.5 g.), b.p. $134^\circ/5$ mm. This was hydrolysed by boiling with HCl (1:2; 250 ml) for 20 hours and the resultant 3-methyl-2-ketopentane-5-carboxylic acid (26 g.), b.p. $137^\circ/5$ mm, was esterified with 5% methanolic HCl (150 ml). This was worked up in the usual way and methyl 3-methyl-2-ketopentane-1-carboxylate was obtained as a colorless oil (25 g.), b.p. $83-85^\circ/5$ mm. (Found: C, 60.4; H, 9.3. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 60.8; H, 8.9%).

2-Methylcyclohex-1,5-dione (IV).—The above ester (21.1 g.) and a solution of sodium (3.1 g.) in absolute methanol (100 ml) were refluxed on a steam bath for 20 hours. The methanol was then evaporated, the residue diluted with ice-water, and carefully acidified with HCl (conc.). The organic matter was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution once washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and then distilled to afford a viscous liquid (12 g.), b.p. $120-25^\circ/3$ mm. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 8.0. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 66.7; H, 7.9%). It gave negative ferric reaction.

3,4-Dimethylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (VI).—The diketone (IV) (10 g.), isobutanol (5 ml), *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.5 g.), and dry benzene (100 ml) were refluxed, using a Dean-Stark water-separator for 6 hours. The cooled solution was poured on a cold saturated solution of NaHCO_3 ; the benzene layer was separated, washed successively with cold 4% NaOH solution and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was evaporated and the residue distilled to furnish the isobutoxy derivative (V) (8.3 g.) which was not analysed; b.p. $110-12^\circ/5$ mm. This was dissolved in ether (15 ml) and added to a Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (15 g.), methyl iodide (4.5 ml), and dry ether (20 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 30 mins., cooled, decomposed with H_2SO_4 (dil.), and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with 2% aqueous NaOH, then with water,

dried (CaCl_2), and the solvent removed. The residue was distilled to provide the sweet-smelling ketone (VI) (3g.), b.p. 78-80°/15 mm. (Found: C, 77.6; H, 9.6. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$: C, 77.4; H, 9.7%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 234 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.16); n_D^{25} 1.4830. Reported data are: λ_{max} 235 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.74)¹⁰, λ_{max} 231 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.02)⁹; n_D^{20} 1.4779⁹ and 1.4702¹⁰.

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute ethanol in white plates, m.p. 198-99°. (Found: C, 59.6; H, 8.5; N, 22.8. Calc. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}_3$: C, 59.7; H, 8.3; N, 23.2%). Reported m.p.s. are 183-84° (ref. 9) and 182-83° (ref. 10). The *dinitrophenylhydrazone* could not be obtained in homogeneous form in spite of repeated crystallisation. The red needles after four crystallisations from benzene-methanol had m.p. 152-60°. (Found: C, 55.3; H, 5.0; N, 18.8. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires C, 55.3; H, 5.3; N, 18.4%). It was possibly a mixture of geometrical isomers. The mixed m.p.s. of the semicarbazones and dinitrophenylhydrazones of the two ketones (III and VI) were considerably depressed.

The author's thanks are due to East India Pharmaceutical Works, Calcutta, for financial assistance to one of them (G.P.) and to Sri B. B. Bhattacharya of the University Colleges of Science and Technology, Calcutta, for microanalyses.